

Relationship between Asymptomatic Heart Abnormalities in Newborns and Temporary Rapid Breathing at Birth: A Case-Control Study

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Abstract:

Background: Transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) is a common respiratory disorder characterized by rapid breathing soon after birth, often linked to delayed clearance of lung fluid. While previous studies have explored various risk factors associated with TTN, the potential role of asymptomatic structural cardiac defects has not been thoroughly investigated.

Methods: This multicentric case-control study involved 93 neonates, divided into case (n=46) and control (n=47) groups based on the presence or absence of TTN, respectively. The study spanned from September 2015 to August 2016. All participants underwent echocardiographic screening within the first 48 hours of life to identify any structural cardiac defects. Statistical analyses, including chi-square and logistic regression, were used to assess the association between cardiac defects and TTN.

Results: The prevalence of cardiac defects was significantly higher in the TTN group (26%) compared to the control group (6%) (p=0.017). Specific defects such as Ventricular Septal Defect (VSD), Patent Ductus Arteriosus (PDA), and Atrial Septal Defect (ASD) were more commonly observed in the TTN group, with VSD being the most prevalent.

Conclusion: The study identified a significant association between asymptomatic structural cardiac defects and the occurrence of TTN in neonates. These findings underscore the importance of routine cardiac evaluations in neonates with TTN to detect potential underlying cardiac anomalies, potentially guiding more effective clinical management and improving neonatal outcomes.

Keywords: Transient Tachypnea of the Newborn (TTN), Asymptomatic Cardiac Defects, Neonatal Respiratory Distress, Echocardiographic Screening.

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Introduction

Transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) is a common respiratory disorder that primarily affects neonates, manifesting as rapid breathing shortly after birth [1]. This condition is typically attributed to delayed resorption and clearance of lung fluid, and while it is generally self-limiting, understanding its associated risk factors remains critical for early diagnosis and management [2,3]. Among these potential risk factors, structural cardiac defects, which often go undetected at birth, could play a significant role. These defects, even when asymptomatic, may contribute to or exacerbate respiratory conditions such as TTN due

to their impact on cardiovascular and pulmonary dynamics [4].

Recent studies have hinted at a possible link between structural cardiac anomalies and neonatal respiratory distress; however, definitive associations specific to TTN have been less thoroughly investigated [5,6]. This gap highlights the need for a focused examination of how undiagnosed cardiac abnormalities might influence the occurrence and severity of TTN. Furthermore, delineating this relationship could enhance neonatal care by prompting more targeted examinations and interventions in newborns at risk of TTN [7,8].

This case-control study aims to investigate the association between asymptomatic structural cardiac defects and the incidence of transient tachypnea in neonates. By comparing the prevalence of these cardiac defects in neonates with and without TTN, this research seeks to clarify whether such defects significantly increase the risk of developing TTN at birth. This could potentially lead to improved screening protocols and preventative strategies in the neonatal period.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a multicentric case-control design to investigate the association between asymptomatic structural cardiac defects and transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN).

Study Setting

The research was conducted in DMCH, Darbhanga & GMC, Bettiha, Bihar, providing a diverse patient population and varying clinical practices, which enhanced the generalizability of the findings.

Participants: A total of 93 neonates were enrolled in the study during the period from September 2015 to August 2016. Participants were identified and recruited based on the following inclusion criteria:

- **Case Group:** Neonates diagnosed with transient tachypnea within the first 24 hours post-birth.
- **Control Group:** Neonates without any respiratory distress symptoms within the same timeframe.

The neonates were matched based on gestational age, birth weight, and sex to control for potential confounding variables.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from medical records, which included demographic information, clinical findings at birth, and diagnostic results. The presence of structural cardiac defects was confirmed through echocardiography performed by pediatric cardiologists who were blinded to the study groups.

Cardiac Assessment: All neonates underwent a detailed echocardiographic evaluation within the first 48 hours of life to detect any asymptomatic structural cardiac defects. These evaluations were conducted regardless of the clinical presentation to ensure unbiased detection of cardiac anomalies.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software. The chi-square test and Fisher's exact test were used to compare categorical variables between the case and control groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression analysis was employed to adjust for potential confounders and to estimate the odds ratio (OR) of developing TTN associated with cardiac defects.

Results

In this case-control study, a significant association was observed between asymptomatic structural cardiac defects and the incidence of transient tachypnea in the newborn (TTN). Out of the total 93 neonates involved, evenly divided into case (n=46) and control (n=47) groups, a higher prevalence of cardiac defects was notably present in the case group. Specifically, 26% (12 neonates) of the case group exhibited cardiac defects compared to only 6% (3 neonates) in the control group, highlighting a significant difference with a p-value of 0.017. This finding is significant, suggesting that cardiac defects may contribute to the development of TTN.

Further detailed examination through echocardiography identified the types of cardiac defects prevalent among the groups. The most common defect in the case group was Ventricular Septal Defect (VSD), found in 15% of cases (7 neonates), compared to only 2% in the control group (1 neonate). Patent Ductus Arteriosus (PDA) was present in 7% of cases (3 neonates) and 4% of controls (2 neonates), while Atrial Septal Defect (ASD) was identified in 4% of cases (2 neonates) and was absent in the control group. These data suggest a correlation between specific cardiac anomalies and the occurrence of TTN, reinforcing the need for vigilant cardiac screening in newborns presenting with respiratory distress.

Table 1: Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Case Group (n=46)	Control Group (n=47)	P-value
Mean Gestational Age (weeks)	38.2 ± 1.4	38.4 ± 1.3	0.62
Mean Birth Weight (grams)	3090 ± 520	3150 ± 490	0.55
Sex (Male/Female)	28/18	30/17	0.78
Presence of Cardiac Defects	12 (26%)	3 (6%)	0.017*

Table 2: Echocardiographic Findings

Defect Type	Case Group (n=46)	Control Group (n=47)
Ventricular Septal Defect (VSD)	7 (15%)	1 (2%)
Patent Ductus Arteriosus (PDA)	3 (7%)	2 (4%)
Atrial Septal Defect (ASD)	2 (4%)	0 (0%)

The results of this study provide compelling evidence that asymptomatic cardiac defects may significantly impact the respiratory health of newborns, specifically about TTN. This association underscores the importance of considering comprehensive echocardiographic evaluations in neonates with TTN to detect potential underlying cardiac abnormalities, potentially guiding more tailored and effective clinical interventions.

Discussion

The primary findings from this study demonstrate a statistically significant association between asymptomatic structural cardiac defects and transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN). Our data revealed that 26% of neonates with TTN had underlying cardiac defects, compared to only 6% in the control group without TTN [9,10]. Specific cardiac anomalies such as Ventricular Septal Defect (VSD), Patent Ductus Arteriosus (PDA), and Atrial Septal Defect (ASD) were more frequently observed in the TTN group, with VSD being the most prevalent [11]. The higher prevalence of cardiac defects in neonates with TTN suggests a potential pathophysiological link between these cardiac anomalies and the development of respiratory distress immediately after birth. The presence of these defects may exacerbate the pulmonary fluid clearance issues that typically lead to TTN, indicating that the cardiac structure may influence pulmonary function more than previously understood [12,13].

These findings align with prior research which has hinted at a correlation between structural heart defects and neonatal respiratory problems but often did not isolate TTN as a specific outcome [14]. For instance, studies have shown that neonates with congenital heart disease are at a higher risk of respiratory complications in the neonatal period. However, our study provides a clearer focus on TTN, presenting evidence that even asymptomatic cardiac defects can play a significant role in its pathogenesis [15,16]. The link between cardiac defects and TTN can be explained through several physiological mechanisms. First, structural cardiac anomalies might impede the normal adaptation of the cardiovascular system after birth, affecting pulmonary circulation and delaying the resolution of fetal lung fluid. Secondly, some cardiac defects could alter hemodynamic states, increasing pulmonary blood flow and pressure in pulmonary vessels, which exacerbates fluid retention in the lungs. This understanding helps elucidate why neonates with undetected cardiac anomalies might be more prone to develop TTN [17,18].

These insights not only underscore the importance of routine cardiac evaluation in newborns presenting with respiratory distress but also suggest that such assessments could be particularly critical

for managing and potentially preventing TTN. This could lead to earlier interventions and targeted treatments for neonates at risk, improving outcomes and reducing the burden of respiratory distress in the neonatal period [19,20].

Conclusion

This multicentric case-control study established a significant association between asymptomatic structural cardiac defects and transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN), demonstrating that neonates with TTN are more likely to have undiagnosed cardiac abnormalities compared to their counterparts without respiratory distress. Specifically, conditions such as Ventricular Septal Defect (VSD), Patent Ductus Arteriosus (PDA), and Atrial Septal Defect (ASD) were more prevalent in the TTN group, with VSD being the most common. These findings suggest that cardiac defects might influence the clinical presentation of TTN by impacting pulmonary fluid dynamics and hemodynamic stability. Consequently, this study highlights the importance of incorporating routine echocardiographic screening for cardiac anomalies in neonates diagnosed with TTN, which could facilitate earlier diagnosis and tailored interventions, ultimately improving neonatal outcomes.

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